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Manuscripts should be addressed to:

Dr. Antonio Mijail Perez
Editor
Gaia Learning
9860 SW 32nd ST
Miami, FL 33165
E-mail: mijail64@gmail.com /
gaia.learning21@gmail.com

Analysis of Carbon Sequestration at an Urban Park in the Miami Dade County

Antonio Mijail Perez, Dora Pilar Maul, & Luis A. Cendan.

St. Thomas University

College of Health Sciences and Technology

1) (C) 786.486.5337, AntonioPerez@stu.edu, 2) (O) 305.628.6603; (C) 772.913.0546, pmaul@stu.edu; dmaul@stu.edu, 3) (C) 786.486.5337, Lcendan@stu.edu

Key words

Biomass, carbon capture, trees, Amelia Earhart Park, Hialeah, South Florida

Abstract

In the context of climate change, scientists strive to look for ways to calculate the constant CO₂ emissions as well as carbon sequestration to find solutions to reduce the emission of greenhouse gases. In this context, it is important to recognize that trees within urban environments operate as “carbon sinks” that significantly contribute to the effort of reducing carbon in the atmosphere. During previous studies in biomass and carbon stock determination conducted in the St. Thomas University campus we have found evidence that “urban forests” play an important role in sequestering carbon from the atmosphere and can serve as a foundation for developing biomass recordings within nearby locations, to support the importance of increasing the number of parks and hardwood trees in urban environments that operate as “carbon sinks”. Our project was conducted in the Amelia Earhart Park, in Hialeah, Florida, with the purpose of calculating the amount of Biomass and Carbon Stock produced by the hardwood trees and palm trees in selected areas of the park. Tree perimeters were measured using a tailor’s tape as a first step to determining their biomass; the height of the trees will be measured using a clinometer. Data transformation and allometric equations were used to determine biomass and carbon stock. The objectives of our project were (1) to determine the average total biomass and carbon stock (expressed in Kg and Mg) in selected locations, 2) compare the biomass and carbon sequestration between hardwood trees and palm trees.

The overall biomass was **706,437.95 Kg (706.44 Mg)**, and overall, Carbon Stock was **332026 Kg (332.02 Mg)**. The area sampled constitutes around 25% of the park land area, so if we extrapolate to the whole land area of the park, we could say that the overall biomass would be roughly **2,825,751.80 Kg (2,825.75 Mg)**, and Carbon Stock ca. **1,328,104 Kg (1,328.10 Mg)**. In order to calculate the totals, we only used Brown & Iverson equation. To express the results by units of area we made the following extrapolations. Total area for Amelia Earhart Park is 208.41 Ha, of which 40% is land area, the rest is water parks, and pools. That 40% represents 83.36 Ha of which we sampled ca. 25% for an effectively sampled area of 20.84 Ha. In conclusion, total Biomass calculated expressed by area is **33.9 Mg Ha⁻¹**, and Carbon Stock is **15.93 Mg Ha⁻¹**. This information strongly supports the importance of increasing the number of parks, and hardwood trees in urban environments that operate as “carbon sinks”, and consequently carbon reservoirs. Total Biomass for Hardwood trees was 689,218.93 Kg (689.22 Mg), and Total biomass for Palm

trees was 17,219.02 Kg (17.22 Mg). Differences in Biomass between hardwood trees, and palm trees, are very significant ($T= 7.67$, $p< 0.01$). Between the palm trees and hardwood, 16 species were identified in different areas of the park. Of the palm trees, *Sabal palmetto* and *Sabal mexicana palm* are the most abundant with over 68 trees total in the park. Of hardwood trees, *Casuarina equisetifolia* and *Quercus virginiana* are the most abundant with over 430 trees combined.

Resumen

En el contexto del cambio climático, los científicos se esfuerzan por buscar formas de calcular las emisiones constantes de CO₂, así como el secuestro de carbono, para encontrar soluciones que reduzcan la emisión de gases de efecto invernadero. En este contexto, es importante reconocer que los árboles dentro de los entornos urbanos funcionan como "sumideros de carbono" que contribuyen significativamente al esfuerzo de reducción de carbono en la atmósfera. Durante estudios previos sobre biomasa y determinación de existencias de carbono realizados en el campus de la Universidad de St. Thomas, hemos encontrado evidencia de que los "bosques urbanos" juegan un papel importante en el secuestro de carbono de la atmósfera y pueden servir como base para desarrollar registros de biomasa en lugares urbanos para apoyar la importancia de aumentar la cantidad de parques y árboles de madera dura en entornos urbanos que funcionan como "sumideros de carbono". Nuestro proyecto se llevó a cabo en el Parque Amelia Earhart, en Hialeah, Florida, con el propósito de calcular la cantidad de Biomasa y Reserva de Carbono producida por los árboles de madera dura y palmeras en áreas seleccionadas del parque. Los perímetros de los árboles se midieron con una cinta de sastre como primer paso para determinar su biomasa; la altura de los árboles se medirá con un clinómetro.

La biomasa total fue de 706.437,95 Kg (706,44 Mg), y la Reserva de Carbono total fue de 332026 Kg (332,02 Mg). El área muestreada constituye alrededor del 25% de la superficie terrestre del parque, por lo que si extrapolamos a toda la superficie terrestre del parque, podríamos decir que la biomasa total sería de aproximadamente 2.825.751,80 Kg (2.825,75 Mg), y el Stock de Carbono ca. 1.328.104 Kg (1.328,10 Mg). Para calcular los totales, solo usamos la ecuación de Brown & Iverson. Para expresar los resultados por unidades de área hicimos las siguientes extrapolaciones. El área total del Parque Amelia Earhart es de 208.41 Ha, de las cuales el 40% es área terrestre, el resto son parques acuáticos y piscinas. Ese 40% representa 83.36 Ha de las cuales muestreamos ca. 25% para un área efectivamente muestreada de 20.84 Ha. En conclusión, la Biomasa total calculada expresada por área es de 33,9 Mg Ha⁻¹ y el Stock de Carbono es de 15,93 Mg Ha⁻¹. Esta información respalda fuertemente la importancia de aumentar la cantidad de parques y árboles maderables en entornos urbanos que funcionan como "sumideros de carbono" y, en consecuencia, reservorios de carbono. La Biomasa Total de 'arboles maderables fue de 689.218,93 Kg (689,22 Mg), y la Biomasa Total de Palma árboles, fue de 17.219,02 Kg (17,22 Mg). Las diferencias en Biomasa entre árboles maderables y palmeras son muy significativas ($T= 7.67$, $p< 0.01$). Entre las palmeras y los árboles maderables, se identificaron 16 especies en diferentes áreas del Parque. De las palmeras, *Sabal palmetto* y *Sabal mexicana palm* son las más abundantes con más de 68 árboles en total en el parque. De los árboles de madera dura, *Casuarina equisetifolia* y *Quercus virginiana* son los más abundantes con más de 430 árboles combinados.

Introduction

The world's forests play a pivotal role in the mitigation of global climate change. Particularly, tropical forests have assumed increasing importance in international efforts to mitigate climate change thanks to their capacity to store carbon and because of the significant emissions caused by their destruction (Malhi & Grace, 2000). Researchers have strived to look for different ways to calculate the constant CO₂ emissions as well as carbon sequestration in order to find solutions to reduce the emission of greenhouse gases and manage the expanding climate change challenge.

Determination of carbon sequestration potential in terrestrial ecosystems through biomass estimation has been the most widely followed approach (Chambers et al., 2001). Biomass is the measure of biological matter expressed in weight and can be applied to individual trees or entire communities across a unit of area. Plant biomass can be subdivided into above ground biomass (AGB) or below ground biomass (BGB) with further subdivisions of each according to the morphology of different species. Scientists calculate the biomass of different tree species using different allometric equations based on tree measurements. The aboveground carbon stock is calculated under the premise that the carbon content is approximately 48% to 50% of the total aboveground biomass (Brown & Lugo, 1982; Dixon, 1994; Cannel, 1995; Richter et al., 1995; Ravindranath et al., 1997).

The urban environment presents important considerations for global climate change. Over half of the world's population lives in urban areas (Population Reference Bureau, 2012). The term "urban forest" refers to all trees within a densely populated area, including trees in parks, on street ways, and on private property. Though the composition, health, age, extent, and costs of urban forests vary considerably among different cities, all urban forests offer some common environmental, economic, and social benefits. Trees in a community help to reduce air and water pollution, alter heating and cooling costs, and increase real estate values. Trees can improve physical and mental health, strengthen social connections, and are associated with reduced crime rates. Trees, community gardens, and other green spaces get people outside, helping to foster active living and neighborhood pride (Safford et al., 2013). In addition, urban forests present important considerations for global climate change. Trees within a densely populated area, including those in parks, on street ways, and on private property, operate as "carbon sinks" that significantly contribute to the effort of reducing carbon in the atmosphere.

This project aimed at collecting information to support the importance of increasing the number of parks and hardwood trees in urban environments that operate as "carbon sinks" as well as identifying tree species that capture the highest amounts of CO₂ within the urban area of our study.

We analyzed the dataset using some equations taken from scientific literature, already used in previous projects (Perez, Cendan, Maul, & Stevenson, 2022). Equations by Brown & Iverson (1992), as well as Nogueira et al., (2008), and others were used to determine biomass and carbon stock. Our study should support ongoing initiatives to not only plant more trees but to select tree species more adept at handling changing climate conditions in South Florida. Moreover, it will allow us to establish a baseline for future studies on changes in tree biomass and carbon capture in response to increasing CO₂ levels in the atmosphere.

Our project was conducted in the Amelia Earhart Park, in the city of Hialeah, Florida, with the purpose of calculating the total amount of Biomass and Carbon Stock produced by trees in selected areas of the park, the contribution from hardwood trees and palm trees, and the amount of carbon dioxide that different tree species sequester from the atmosphere. Tree perimeters were measured using a tailor's tape as a first step to determining their biomass; the height of the trees was also measured using a clinometer.

Material & Methods

Study Site: The project was conducted in Amelia Earhart Park, City of Hialeah. The 515-acre (208.4 Ha.) park is situated just south of the Miami-Opa Locka Executive Airport and offers a series of recreational attractions together with wide green spaces with winding pathways beneath trees of over 20 different species. 40% of the park (83.4 Ha) is land area, the rest is water parks and pools. We selected a 21 Ha. area (ca. 25% of the land area) in the park for sampling, an area that contains a diversity of tree species including hardwood trees and palm trees. Tree species were identified using taxonomical keys.

Figure 1.-

Sampled area in Amelia Earhart Park.

We measured Tree perimeters in centimeters using a Tailor's tape on hardwood tree species and palm trees, as a first step to determining their biomass. We also measured the height of the trees using a clinometer.

Figure 2.

Measurement of Diameter/ Perimeter.

Analysis: We transformed perimeters (at Breast Height, = 130 cm) into diameters. To determine biomass and carbon stock we used equations taken from the scientific literature, already used in previous projects: equations by Brown & Iverson (1992), as well as Nogueira et al., (2008), for Hardwood Trees, and Donkor et al., (2016), for Palm Trees. The equations are as follows:

For Hardwood Trees:

Brown & Iverson (1992): $Y \text{ (Kg/tree)} = 21.297 - 6.953 \text{ (DBH)} + 0.740 \text{ (DBH)}^2$

Nogueira et al. (2008):

$$\ln(Y) = -1.716 + 2.413 * \ln \text{DBH}$$

$$Y = e[-1.716 + 2.413 * \ln \text{DBH}]$$

E= euler

For Palm Trees:

Donkor et al., (2016)

$$Y = 0.00388 \times (\text{DBH}^2)^{1.6063}$$

Analysis of Carbon stock: We calculated the aboveground biomass, and carbon stock by assuming that the carbon content is approximately 47% of the total aboveground biomass (Brown & Lugo, 1982; Dixon, 1994; Cannel, 1995; Richter et al., 1995; Ravindranath, Somashekhar, & Gadgil, 1997).

$$\text{Carbon} = \text{Biomass} \times 0.47.$$

The dataset obtained was analyzed to address the hypotheses of this study. All statistical analyses were conducted using Excel Data Analysis add-in, and PAST (Øyvind, Harper & Ryan, 2008).

Results

General Results: Overall biomass was 706,437.95 Kg (706.44 Mg), and overall, Carbon Stock was 332026 Kg (332.02 Mg). The area sampled constitutes around 25% of the park land area, so if we extrapolate to the whole land area of the park, we could say that the overall biomass would be roughly 2,825,751.80 Kg (2,825.75 Mg), and Carbon Stock ca. 1,328,104 Kg (1,328.10 Mg). In order to calculate the totals, we only used Brown & Iverson (1992) equation, since it's the one that yielded the highest Determination Coefficient for this study ($r^2 = 0.89$) (Fig. 3, Fig. 4, Table 1-Table 4).

To express the results by units of area we made the following extrapolations. We know from the web (Wikipedia, 2002), that total area for Amelia Earhart Park is 208.41 Ha, of which using Google Earth maps concluded that 40% is land area, the rest is water parks and pools. That 40% represents 83.36 Ha of which we sampled ca. 25% for an effectively sampled area of 20.84 Ha. In conclusion, the total Biomass calculated expressed by area is 33.9 Mg Ha^{-1} , and the Carbon Stock is 15.93 Mg Ha^{-1} .

Table 1.-
Overall biomass calculated.

<i>Bio B&I,92-W</i>	
Mean	1209.65403
Standard Deviation	1569.24774
Minimum	33.5597349
Maximum	13883.8063
Sum	706437.954
Count	584

Table 2.-
Overall carbon stock calculated.

<i>CO (0.47)</i>	
Mean	568.537394
Standard Deviation	737.546439
Minimum	15.7730754
Maximum	6525.38896
Sum	332025.838
Count	584

Figure 3.-
Best fit line between Diameter and Biomass using the Brown & Iverson (1992) allometric equation.

Table 3.-
Basic stats for the relationship between Diameter and Biomass using Brown & Iverson (1992) allometric equation.

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.945375426
R Square	0.893734695
Adjusted R Square	0.89351377
Standard Error	536.2547291
Observations	483

Figure 4.-
Best fit line between Diameter and Biomass using the Nogueira (2008) allometric equation.

Table 4.-
Basic stats for the relationship between Diameter and Biomass using Nogueira (2008) allometric equation.

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.913105449
R Square	0.833761562
Adjusted R Square	0.833415951
Standard Error	1256.871713
Observations	483

Species composition and Abundance: In the data collected between the palm trees and hardwood, 16 species were identified in different areas of the Amelia Earhart Park. Of the palm trees, *Sabal palmetto* and *Sabal mexicana palm* are the most abundant with over 68 trees total in the park. Of hardwood trees, *Casuarina equisetifolia* and *Quercus virginiana* are the most abundant with over 430 trees combined in the park (Figures 5 to 8).

Figure 5.-
Australian she oak - Casuarina equisetifolia

Figure 6.-
Southern live oak - Quercus virginiana

Figure 7.-
Sabal palm - Sabal palmetto

Figure 8.-
Mexican palmetto - Sabal mexicana

Hardwood and Palm trees: We collected information to support the importance of increasing the number of parks, and hardwood trees in urban environments that operate as “carbon sinks”, and consequently carbon reservoirs. Total Biomass for Hardwood trees was 689,218.93 Kg (689.22 Mg), and Total biomass for Palm Trees, was 17,219.02 Kg (17.22 Mg) (Tables 5 & Table 6).

Table 5.-

Basic Stats Biomass for all Three Formulas for Hardwood and Palm Trees.

Stats	B&I, 1992	Nogueira, 2008	Donkor, 2016
Mean	1426.95	2265.85	170.49
Standard Deviation	1643.33	3079.46	145.98
Minimum	35.68	60.55	33.56
Maximum	13883.81	28081.96	1158.49
Sum	689218.93	1094407.01	17219.02
Count	483	483	101

Table 6.-

Basic Stats Carbon Stock for all Three Formulas for Hardwood and Palm Trees.

Stats	B&I, 1992	Nogueira, 2008	Donkor, 2016
Mean	670.67	1064.95	80.13
Standard Deviation	772.36	1447.34	68.61
Minimum	16.77	28.46	15.77
Maximum	6525.39	13198.52	544.49
Sum	323932.9	514371.3	8092.94
Count	483	483	101

Differences in Biomass based on Brown & Iverson (1992) allometric equation, as well as Donkor (2016) allometric equation for Palm Trees, is very significant ($T= 7.67$, $p< 0.01$). We obtained the same value in the T Test conducted between both Carbon Stocks compared, so differences are equally very significant.

Biomass of most important tree species: The calculated biomass, and carbon stock of the most important tree species present in Amelia Earhart Park, are shown in kilograms (kg) in Tables 7 to 10, and figures from 9 and 10. These four species make up 77% of the whole set of trees measured in the area (584 trees).

Table 7.-

Biomass using Brown & Iverson's and Donkor's Equations, for Hardwood and Palm Trees respectively.

Stats	<i>Quercus virginiana</i>	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>	<i>Sabal palmetto</i>	<i>Sabal mexicana</i>
Average	881.99	3787.92	133.97	452.80
Standard Deviation	801.68	2886.05	55.08	61.21
Min	42.05	354.12	50.60	365.17
Max	8083.18	13120.40	330.43	507.82
Sum	248722.34	378791.90	8574.15	1811.18
Count	282	100.00	64.00	4.00

Figure 9.-

Biomass contribution from most important species using Brown & Iverson's and Donkor's Equations, for Hardwood and Palm Trees respectively.

Table 8.-

Carbon Stock using Brown & Iverson's and Donkor's Equations, for Hardwood and Palm Trees respectively.

Stats	<i>Quercus virginiana</i>	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>	<i>Sabal palmetto</i>	<i>Sabal mexicana</i>
Average	414.54	1780.32	62.97	212.81
Standard Deviation	376.79	1356.44	25.89	28.77
Min	19.76	166.44	23.78	171.63
Max	3799.09	6166.59	155.30	238.68
Sum	116899.50	178032.19	4029.85	851.26
Count	282	100	64	4

Figure 10.-

Carbon Stock contribution from most important species using Brown & Iverson's and Donkor's Equations, for Hardwood and Palm Trees respectively.

Table 9.-

Biomass using Nogueira's and Donkor's Equations, for Hardwood and Palm Trees respectively.

Stats	<i>Q. virginiana</i>	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>
Average	1310.01	6589.99
Standard Deviation	1355.73	5723.08
Min	69.24	487.03
Max	14977.07	26288.26
Sum	369423.81	658999.36
Count	282	100

Table 10.-

Carbon Stock using Nogueira's Equation.

Stats	<i>Q. virginiana</i>	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>
Average	615.71	3097.30
Standard Deviation	637.19	2689.85
Min	32.54	228.91
Max	7039.23	12355.48
Sum	173629.19	309729.70
Count	282	100

Discussion

According to Perez et al (2022), total Biomass calculated from all tree species in the STU forest was 561.43 Mg or 17.54 Mg Ha⁻¹ (Mean 1098.70, SD 881.78, Range 134.97-6,169.62, N= 511), or 561,428.30 Kg (Table 1). Becknell et al., (2012) in their study on seasonally dry tropical forests (SDTFs) obtained a biomass of 39 to 334 Mg ha⁻¹, which is a much higher amount than the one obtained in our study, but it may be due to the fact that the campus forest has wide gaps, with no trees.

In a tropical dry forest in northwestern Mexico, Navar (2008), obtained 73 Mg ha⁻¹ for total above ground biomass, although they not only used the DBH but also the trunk specific gravity, which is added to the DBH. Their data was obtained from 637 trees. Other results are not comparable because they encompass not only AGB, but also BGB, such as the ones from Donkor and others (2016).

In Table 11 we present results for total aboveground biomass from Brown et al., (1992), collected in forests from Peninsular Malaysia. At a first glance we notice that Disturbed forests produce much less biomass that undisturbed for a rather similar area.

Table 11.-

Total aboveground biomass from Brown et al., (1992), collected in forests from Peninsular Malaysia.

Forest Class	AGB (Mg/ Ha)	Area (10 ³ ha)
Undisturbed Forests	270	3,564
Primary hill	279	2,742
Moderate hill	250(25)	1,143
Good hill	288(29)	916
Superior hill	315(31)	683
Restricted hill	242	542
Poor hill	19(18)	261
Upper hill	287(28)	281
Swamps		
Freshwater	233(22)	280
Disturbed Forests	192	3,258
Hill	191	2,943
Logged after 1966	191(18)	2,246
Logged before 1996	209(20)	481
Shifting cultivation	145(14)	216
Swamp	209	315
Logged after 1966	196(18)	276
Logged before 1996	302(28)	39
All Forest Classes	233	6,943

Alves et al., (1997), obtained similar results studying the Biomass of primary and secondary vegetation in Rondonia, Western Brazilian Amazon. In Table 12 below, we can see that aboveground biomass in primary forests was greater than biomass in any other forest type, all of them less mature, regardless of the allometric equation, since they used 11 equations.

Table 12.-

Biomass [above-ground dry weight ($t\ ha^{-1}$)] estimates by 11 allometric equations and the fraction of primary forest biomass represented by the 18-year-old biomass.

Equation	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
A (prim for)	453	458	427	398	495	332	291	354	428	347	409
B (18-year-old)	273	275	223	176	213	169	163	143			
C (16-year-old)	216	218	167	106	128	124	107	103			
D (11-year-old)	141	142	103	65	100	62	73	63			
E (9-year-old)	187	190	133	70	116	72	79	90			
F (5-year-old)	99	100	65	36	44	46	41	38			
G (3-year-old)	78	79	44	33	42	33	38	33			
H (3-year-old)	98	99	47	27	34	34	33	37			
I (2-year-old)	18	18	9	4	7	5	6	7			

Conclusions

Overall biomass was 706,437.95 Kg (706.44 Mg), and overall, Carbon Stock was 332026 Kg (332.02 Mg). The area sampled constitutes around 25% of the park land area, so if we extrapolate to the whole land area of the park, we could say that the overall biomass would be roughly 2,825,751.80 Kg (2,825.75 Mg), and Carbon Stock ca. 1,328,104 Kg (1,328.10 Mg). To calculate the totals, we only used Brown & Iverson (1992) equation, since it's the one that yielded the highest Determination Coefficient for this study ($r^2= 0.89$).

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